

Supplementary information for “Supplementary information for “Assessment of permafrost related hazards in China based on Chinese literature”

S1. Systematic literature review method

Literature search was accomplished in China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI, <https://www.cnki.net/index/>). The scoping search was conducted on 4 April 2023 with no time restrictions. We adopted “permafrost debris flow”, “permafrost landslide”, “permafrost thaw slump”, “permafrost hazard”, and “permafrost collapse” as keywords. The number of publications were as follows: permafrost thaw slump (n = 127), permafrost hazard (n = 55), permafrost landslide (n = 30), permafrost debris flow (n = 3), permafrost collapse (n = 3).

Figure S1: Reporting standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses (ROSES) flow diagram

The initial pilot research in the CNKI database resulted in 218 potentially relevant Chinese publications, of which 25 duplicates were removed. After reviewing the titles and abstracts, 65 publications remained. The initial research produced 65 publications for full review. All the data were extracted and quantified from these publications which were the primary database of this summary article. From the residual 65 publications, 53 publications were inside the HMA area. Only Chinese publications in the HMA area were considered for this review. 4 publications concerned Xinjiang Province which is out of the HKH area. The rest of the 49 publications were all in HKH as well as QTP. All the research conducted by Chinese scientists in HKH region is on the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau. Additionally, 49% of the QTP research concerned the Qinghai-Tibet Engineering Corridor, including railways, roads, pipelines, and cables. For the rest 25 publications, 11 didn't mention infrastructure, 10 focused on other roads on the QTP, and the other 3 were about buildings, cables, and collieries, respectively (Figure S1).

There are only three Chinese publications on permafrost in HMA before 2000; number of publications grew rapidly after the 21st century. Chinese scientists published 20 studies in the first decade, 30 studies in the second decade. In the first three years of this decade, there are already 10 studies (Figure S2). A National Basic Research Program (973 program) called "Basic Research on the Major Permafrost Projects in the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau" was officially launched in April 2012 (Ma et al., 2012). Among the 53 selected publications, 49 were focused on the QTP, of which 24 studies concentrated on the Qinghai-Tibet Engineering Corridor (Figure S1, e.g., Luo et al., 2014; Ma et al., 2012). There are 90 distinct locations in our database, of which 8 covered the whole plateau, 59 sites were identified in mountain areas, and the remaining 23 were in basins (Figure S2a). Most of the study areas were located in Kunlun Shan and Tangola Shan. 12 study areas were in Kunlun Shan, 8 in Xidatan (Kunlun Shan), 6 in Fenghuo Shan (Kunlun Shan) and 5 in Hoh Xil Hills (Kunlun Shan). Hence, there are a total of 31 study areas in Kunlun Shan (e.g., Ma et al., 2004; Niu et al., 2011; Wang, 2013). 17 study areas were located in the Tangola Shan, mountain range (e.g., Liu et al., 2003; Liu, 2015; Quan, 2013). In basins, Beiluhe Basin has the most study areas – 11 sites (e.g., Jin et al., 2006; Ma et al., 2006; Niu et al., 2002). Qumarhe Basin and Tuotuohe Basin owned 4 and 3 sites, respectively.

121 hazards were recorded in the reviewed publications. We divided the hazards into 13 categories (Figure S2b). More than 25% of publications were relevant to thaw slumps (n=31, e.g., Ci et al., 2006; Ma et al., 2012), 17% mentioned frost heaving (n=21, e.g., Li, 2013; Liu et al., 2020; Wang et al., 1979), 12% were on thaw settlement

(n=15, e.g., Li et al., 2003; Wang, 2020), and 10% focused on thermokarst lakes (n=12, e.g., Lin et al., 2008; Wang, 2013). Each of the remaining hazards were less than 10 percent of the total. The hazards occurred in different parts of HMA (Figure 2). There is a significant negative correlation between the extent of permafrost and the occurrence of disasters such as collapses, landslides, and debris flows. As the area of permafrost decreases, the number of various geological disasters shows a noticeable increasing trend. Moreover, the spatial distribution of geological disasters is largely consistent with the extent of permafrost degradation (Chen, 2021).

Figure S2: Distribution of publications in each study area and hazard type

S2. Statistical analyses

Statistical analyses were performed in R version 4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2023). Variation partitioning analysis (VPA) was used to determine the impacts of environmental factors and interactions between different parameters on permafrost thickness (“varpart” function in vegan package).

S3. Permafrost Hazards

The current pace of warming observed in numerous regions across China, notably within the permafrost areas of the QTP, is unprecedented (Ehlers et al., 2022; Li et al., 2015) with major implications on human systems and ecosystems (Yi et al., 2014). Permafrost landscape changes and increase in frequency and distribution of hazards: mass movements, ground subsidence, ecological changes and engineering challenges are widespread (Wang et al., 2020; Guo et al., 2018; Hjort et al., 2022). In western China, permafrost active layer deepening causes hydrological shifts: increase in river runoff, expansion of lake areas, and deepening of lakes (Zongxing et al., 2019).

S3.1 Thaw slumps

Thaw slumps affect properties of soil in the permafrost active layer, intensify ablation and release meltwater to accumulate at areas without proper drainage forming thermokarst lakes (Wang et al., 2018) Anthropogenic disturbances, fluvio-thermal processes, weakening of basal slopes, exposure of permafrost ice, and thawing due to high air temperatures and intense precipitation are major responsible factors for these slope movements (Niu et al., 2016).

Increased susceptibility of retrogressive thaw slumps is observed on the Central Tibetan Plateau with ice-rich permafrost indicating that mass movements through thaw slumps are strongly associated with the volumetric ice content (Jiao et al., 2022). Between 2018 and 2020, remote sensing observations detected more than 2600 retrogressive thaw slumps on slopes below 10° in the northern quadrant in permafrost areas of the QTP triggered due to warm conditions during summer months (Luo et al., 2022). In Beiluhe region of the QTP, frequency of thaw slump events and the area occupied increased dramatically by more than 250% and 600% respectively between 2008 and 2017. These events were not progressive over the years but were intense during 2010 and 2016 due to unusually high temperatures and heavy precipitation (Luo et al., 2019).

S3.2 Landslide

Regional increase in temperatures cause substantial thawing and degradation of permafrost resulting in increased outflow of water and extensive infiltration during intense summer rainfall events thus increasing the soil moisture content and producing large number of landslides. In 2000-2019, sudden and intense temperature and precipitation, and decreasing snow covers in northwest China caused an exponential increase in landslide events, mainly occurring during warmer quarters of the year. These landslides were more frequent at elevations beyond 4500 m asl, suggesting high sensitivity to temperature and high susceptibility to landslides of mountain slopes in this elevation range (Pei et al., 2023).

S3.3 Permafrost collapse

On the eastern part, there was a dramatic increase in permafrost collapse area between 1969 and 2017 with most of the area (more than two-thirds) being increased after 2004 (Gao et al., 2021). In the northeastern Tibetan Plateau, permafrost collapse considerably reduced around 30 % of soil carbon and nitrogen from the top 10 cm of the permafrost soil (Mu et al., 2016).

S3.4 Ecosystem services

Ecosystem services in high mountain areas are vulnerable to climate warming led retreat of glaciers, reduction of permafrost areas, varying river discharge, changes in vegetation patterns, and occurrence of hazards (Schirpke et al., 2021). Although locally, warming led decrease in permafrost thickness and area appear as important factors for degradation of rangelands on the Qinghai-Tibetan plateau (Harris, 2010). Wetlands in several parts of China, including the Tibetan Plateau, are shrinking on account of climate warming and permafrost thawing led intensification of soil water evaporation and runoff reductions (Meng et al., 2017). Increasing temperatures and thawing permafrost could lead to a more wet or dry ecosystem depending upon the timescale, soil permeability and drainage (Jin et al., 2021); ultimately, under continued warming and thawing, a dry ecosystem persists. Quantitative analysis of mass wasting and sediment migration due to ablation of ice-rich permafrost is effective in understanding the ecological impacts of permafrost hazards such as thaw slumps (Jiao et al., 2023).

S3.5 Infrastructure

Engineering challenges on the QTP originate due to the occurrence and distribution of permafrost ice, changes in frozen ground conditions due to warming, and the impact of engineered structures on permafrost. For example, damages to highways are mainly due to frost heave, thaw related surface and subsurface deformations, and longitudinal cracks following complex hydrothermal interactions between the ground surface and the weight of the overlying structures (Sha et al., 2022).

Anthropogenic disturbances during infrastructure construction are found responsible for instigating multiple hazards; for instance, in Tibet, even small hydropower development involves use of explosives and construction of permanent civil structures capable of introducing substantial conflicts, such as erosion and mass wasting, in permafrost environments (Pang et al., 2018).

The Qinghai-Tibet Railway (QTR), Qinghai-Tibet Highway (QTH), Qinghai-Tibet DC power transmission line, and China-Russia crude oil pipeline are some of the major infrastructure at risk due to thawing permafrost. Impacts and hazards associated with climate change in China are geographically diverse due to complex climate systems and social structures (Ding et al., 2021).

S3.6 Adaptation

Express highway networks built in the last three decades in China primarily fulfil the demands of increasing number of people in the region and assist in economic growth of the nation. Large sections of these networks are built on permafrost; substantial engineering efforts, necessary to construct and maintain these networks, have been made to overcome difficulties brought about by degrading permafrost due to climate crisis and infrastructure developments (Wang et al., 2020). Ground subsidence due to thaw consolidation is a major mechanical threat often mitigated through effective heat convection arrangements. Temperature reduction using air convection embankments is extensively applied across linear infrastructure such as highways in China (Doré et al., 2016). Increase in average temperatures by 1°C can be accommodated through these embankments built using crushed

rocks (Wu et al., 2020). Thermosyphons and asphalt pavements are other structures used for express highways to reduce temperatures through heat-transfer (Wang et al., 2020). Constructions should focus on lowering the temperatures of permafrost below the structures through regulating heat convection and conduction rather than increasing capacity of structures to withstand heat (Wei et al., 2009). For gas pipelines, changing permafrost conditions and expansion of pipelines have made it compulsory to use adaptive measures such as thermosyphons and thermal insulation layers while advanced methods are found necessary for future mitigation strategies (Li et al., 2022b).

Megaprojects like Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), that traverses through wide-ranging areas with permafrost, should consider ecological economics and human systems in these areas (Hughes et al., 2020). Such projects should assess the potential impacts on ecology and environment and carefully weigh the confirmed and optimistic socio-economic impacts against likely ecological and environmental insecurities and challenges to sustainable development that it will invite in the context of climate warming (Zhang et al., 2021). Adequate concern and planning, and appropriate amendments in engineering practices are necessary to address the onset of hazards brought about by these developments.

S3.7 Projections

About 35% of permafrost regime on the QTP, which cover human settlements with almost 120000 people, more than 1600 km stretch of the QTH, 650 km section of the QTR and more than 3 Gigatons of carbon, is highly vulnerable to degradation (Li et al., 2022a). Nearly 40% settlement areas at the periphery of existing permafrost along the Qinghai-Tibet Railway are found to be at high risk due to permafrost ice melt (Ni et al., 2021). An obvious increase in soil temperature – more than 3°C – in QTEC by the end of this century. Settlement related hazards are confirmed for more than 30% area of the QTEC by 2050; QTH and QTR occupy about one half of this area (Guo and Sun, 2015). Increase in active layer thickness – up to 200 cm – can be observed for several areas on the QTP (Peng et al., 2018).

Table S1: Permafrost types according to their ice content

Classification	Total water content of permafrost (%)			Coefficient of thaw settlement (%)	Thaw settlement level
	Gravel soil	Sandy soil	Silty soil and clayey soil		
Low-ice content	< 10	< 12	< W_p	< 1	No thaw settlement
High-ice content	10 – 18	12 - 21	$W_p < W < 0.9 W_L$	1 – 5	Weak thaw settlement
Ice-rich	18 – 25	21 - 28	$0.9W_L < W < 1.2 W_L$	5 – 10	Thaw settlement
Ice-saturated	25 – 65	28 - 65	$1.2W_L < W < 70 - 80$	10 – 40	Strong thaw settlement
Ice-layer with soil	> 65	> 65	> 70 - 80	> 40	Strong thaw subsidence

Note: W_p is soil plastic limit, W_L is soil liquid limit.

Table S2: Permafrost types according to their MAGT

Classification	Low Temperature Stable Permafrost	Low Temperature Marginally Stable Permafrost	High Temperature Semi-Stable Permafrost	High Temperature Unstable Permafrost
MAGT (°C)	$T_{cp} < -2$	$-2 \leq T_{cp} < -1$	$-1 \leq T_{cp} < -0.5$	$-0.5 \leq T_{cp}$

Note: T_{cp} is temperature-controlled pile

Table S3: Permafrost types according to their continuity

Classification	Continuity (%)
Continuous permafrost	> 65
Discontinuous permafrost	30 - 65
Island permafrost	5 – 30

Figure S3: Maximum and minimum active layer thickness and permafrost thickness variation with MAAT and MAGT

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